

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)

January 1, 2022 – December 31, 2022

End of Year Evaluation Report

Contents

Abbreviations	3
Executive Summary	4
I. Background	7
Overview of the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation	8
II. Methods	9
Data Sources	9
RP2 Program Records	10
Project Intake Survey	10
Bimonthly Evaluation Surveys	10
Follow-up Survey (6-month post closeout)	10
Data Analysis	11
Individual Dashboards	11
Quarterly Aggregate Dashboards	11
Biannual T&E Evaluation Reports	11
Project Impact Profiles	12
Most Significant Change	13
III. Results	13
A. Process Evaluation Results	13
RP2 Program Grant Application Process and Award Utilization	13
B. Outcome Evaluation Results	15
B1. Participant Completion Rates	15
B2. Sociodemographic Results	16
Characteristics of RP2 Projects	16
Underserved Populations Served	17
COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served	18
Characteristics of RP2 Projects' Partners	18
B3. RP2 Project Testing and Enrollment Outcomes	19
RP2 Projects Testing and Enrollment	19
Challenges Experienced by Projects	20
B3. RP2 Project Outcomes and Impacts	21

IV. Recommendations and Conclusion	22
References	25
Appendix	26
Appendix 1. RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model	26
Appendix 2. RADx-UP RP2 Quarterly Dashboard Report	27
Appendix 3. RADx-UP RP2 Impact Profile	28

Abbreviations

CCPH	Campus Community Partners for Health
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CHER	UNC Center for Health Equity Research
C2G	Community Collaboration Grant
DA	Data Analytics
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
EO	Evaluation Objective
EQ	Evaluation Question
MSC	Most Significant Change
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PI	Principal Investigator
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations
RP2	Rapid Research Pilot Program
SEBI	Social, ethical, and behavioral implications
SECDP	Stakeholder Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination Plan
SEP	Strategic Evaluation Plan
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
UNC	The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
US	United States

Executive Summary

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality. The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) aims to award up to \$200,000 used within a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved in coordination with the NIH-supported RADx initiatives¹. Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding¹. RP2 projects are human subject research studies requiring approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB).

This year one end of year evaluation report details the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program's (RP2) key evaluation findings that indicate RADx-UP RP2 program outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts between January 1, 2022 through December 31, 2022. This report also presents an opportunity for collaboration with RADx-UP, Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC), and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC) employs a longitudinal design utilizing a mixed-methods approach. The T&E team collects data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and CDCC support and resources used by the awardees at a minimum of seven time points (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model](#)). The T&E team is responsible for distributing the bimonthly surveys, analyzing the data, and communicating the results to RP2 leadership and other stakeholders.

RP2 Program Evaluation Overview

The outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impact of the RP2 program were measured using data already collected by the CDCC (project intake & characteristics), publicly available publication data, and bimonthly evaluation surveys.

- As of January 12, 2023, the **CDCC has funded 19 RP2 projects across six funding cycles.**

- The projects are separated by cycle, with **cycle 1** projects beginning in August/September of 2021, **cycle 2** projects beginning in November 2021, **cycle 4** projects beginning in March 2022, **cycle 5** projects beginning in September 2022, and **cycle 6** projects beginning in February 2023.

RP2 Project Geographic Diversity

- This report is reporting on data from project cycles 1-2 and 4-5. There were no funded projects for cycle 3, and cycle 6 has not yet begun data collection.
- Most RP2 projects are in the Midwest, South, and Southwest regions.
- The most common underserved populations targeted by the RP2 projects include **socioeconomically disadvantaged people, people living in nursing homes and assisted living facilities, and Hispanic/Latino populations.**

Program Enrollment

- As of December 31, 2022 the current funded RP2 projects have enrolled **1,778 participants of the 4,120 participants (43.2%) that they are targeting to enroll over the course of their project period.**

Program Testing

- The current funded RP2 projects have administered **a total of 2,099 tests of the 8,600 they are targeting to administer (24.4%) over the course of their project period.**

Challenges and Barriers

- The most common challenges reported by the projects (n=12) include **enrollment challenges and testing reporting challenges.**

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the T&E team provides two main recommendations for improving the Rapid Research Pilot Program. These recommendations aim to support continuous program improvement, program delivery, and quality of administrative support.

1. **Continue to fund a diverse range of projects to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have**

**Enrollment challenges* are defined as challenges in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site has been established. *Testing reporting* challenges are defined as challenges in obtaining results from tests or reporting test results to patients.

2. Increase access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.

- Focus marketing and communication efforts on recruiting additional applicants for future cycles
- Continue to fund projects representing geographically diverse, underserved, and Covid-19 vulnerable communities. Some populations to focus on recruiting in the future can include –
 - West, Northwest, and Eastern regions of the US
 - Recruiting projects that represent tribal nations
 - States where there is an increased COVID-19 incidence and/or mortality rate

3. Address challenges cited by projects

- Projects report challenges related to participant enrollment, administrative tasks such as funding and staffing, testing reporting, and testing administration.
- Of the 12 projects that reported on challenges experienced, **the most common were related to enrollment and testing reporting challenges.**
- Maintaining **continuous feedback loops** between the UNC T&E team, the RP2 Leadership team, and RP2 awardees. The figure below illustrates how these feedback loops work amongst the teams- the T&E team reports findings to the RP2 Leadership team, and in turn the RP2 Leadership team communicates this to the RP2 funded projects. Should any questions or concerns arise, the RP2 funded projects will communicate back to the RP2 Leadership team.

Feedback loops between T&E team, RP2 leadership team, and RP2 awardees

I. Background

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.

The program seeks to achieve this primary aim through:

- Understanding and alleviating barriers to testing across the nation
- Utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved
- Strengthening the available data on disparities in infection rates, disease progression, and outcomes; differences in testing access and uptake patterns; and identifying strategies to address inequities in COVID-19 diagnostics

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supports RADx-UP projects as they serve their communities. The CDCC serves as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research (CHER) at the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, oversee the CDCC.

This 2022 Annual RP2 Evaluation Report explicitly covers the evaluation of **the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)** projects from January 1 through December 31, 2022. In coordination with the National Institutes of Health (NIH) supported RADx initiatives ¹, the **Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)** awards up to \$200,000 in direct costs for a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in underserved geographic locations ¹. Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding ¹. RP2 projects are human subject research studies requiring approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB).

These evaluation results are used by the RP2 team to address any issues with awardees in ad hoc meetings and to improve CDCC support and overall understanding of each project's progress towards reaching their intended goals.

Overview of the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC), comprehensively assesses the RADx-UP program’s productivity and impact by evaluating its projects. The T&E team employs the core components of the **Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model**² to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large. The team also employs the **Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework** to address individual-level and organization-level outcomes and impacts significant to measuring the sustainability and effectiveness of programs^{3,4}. The RE-AIM components are used to evaluate the wide reach, sustainable adoption, implementation processes and long term effects of the RP2 program. The team also employs the **Most Significant Change (MSC) approach** to better understand program impact, and the values held by different stakeholders⁵.

An overview of the RADx-UP RP2 aims, outcomes and associated evaluation key measures are available in **Table 1**. The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the RADx-UP program’s effectiveness, performance, and community engagement.

The purpose of this report is two-fold: 1) describe key evaluation findings that indicate **RADx-UP RP2 program** outputs, outcomes, productivity, and; 2). collaborate with RADx-UP, CDCC, and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

Table 1. Overview of RADx-UP RP2 Aims, Outcomes, and Associated Evaluation Key Measures

Overview of Outcomes and Key Measures		
Outcomes	Measures	Survey Tools Used
Aim 1: Improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations.		
Increase in individuals reached with testing services or information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of individuals reached through projects (enrolled) • Number of individuals tested • Number of positive tests • Frequency of testing per participant • Number of participants showing one or more symptoms • Underserved populations and COVID-19 vulnerable populations engaged through projects (per cycle and cumulatively) 	Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of populations reached (geographically, across underserved and vulnerable population categories) 	
<p>Aim 2: Evaluate the feasibility of implementing emerging COVID-19 testing technologies in underserved communities.</p>		
<p>Participants enrolled in each study</p> <p>Expanded RADx-UP Resource Library</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of organizations funded (location, organization type) # of new materials/resources added to Resource Library Number and type of research products resulting from pilot project (publication, new external grant, etc.) 	<p>Program Records</p> <p>Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap</p>
<p>Aim 3: Implement the RP2 program to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.</p>		
<p>Recruitment of a sufficient number of applicants</p> <p>Timely launch of projects</p> <p>Timely completion of projects</p> <p>Feedback on utility and quality support</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # of applicants per cycle # of projects awarded per cycle # of days between award notification and project initiation Utilization of RADx-UP resources and support % of awardees that expended funding in a 12-month grant period Types of CDCC support used Suggested improvements to CDCC support/resources 	<p>Program Records</p> <p>Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap</p>

II. Methods

Data Sources. The RADx-UP RP2 evaluation consists of a longitudinal evaluation design, which involves collecting data from RP2 program awardees at seven time points. Data collected includes project updates, activities, outcomes, and use of CDCC support and resources (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model](#)). Data sources include RP2 program records, project intake surveys, bimonthly evaluation surveys, and a follow-up evaluation survey six months after the closeout of the program. See [Figure 1](#) for a flow diagram of how the data sources map onto program evaluation.

RP2 Program Records

The RP2 grant administration leadership team works with the T&E team to provide grant administration data such as the number of applicants per cycle.

Project Intake Survey

The T&E team retrieves demographic data on the project target population(s) and project characteristics from the Project Intake Survey completed by the project team at enrollment.

Bimonthly Evaluation Surveys

The T&E team administers bimonthly progress report surveys through REDCap to RP2 awardees based on project start dates. Bimonthly evaluation surveys collect information on project testing and enrollment, challenges faced in completing the program; protocol changes; and tracking self-assessment on meeting milestones. Items on these surveys also assess components of the RE-AIM framework.

The 6-month and closeout surveys contain additional questions to gather data on project outcomes, research productivity and dissemination of findings; utilization of RADx-UP CDCC support; and community partner engagement. Items on these evaluation surveys also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the TSBM Framework indicators.

Extended Timelines

The original evaluation data collection plan included bimonthly evaluation surveys up to month 10 of the projects, followed by a 12-month closeout evaluation survey. Given that there have been a number of projects that have extended their original project timeline, the T&E team has worked with the RP2 leadership team to revise the data collection plan. Additional bimonthly surveys have been added to the data collection schedule based on each project's new timeline, followed by a closeout evaluation survey two months after the last bimonthly evaluation survey. Overall the basic structure of data collection is the same, with a regular cadence of bimonthly evaluation surveys being distributed, but this new structure takes into account the changing timelines of the projects.

Follow-up Survey (6-month post closeout)

The T&E team administers a follow-up survey at six months after project completion via REDCap to assess the long-term impacts of the pilot projects. This evaluation includes any sustained project activities and other achievements from the pilot project (such as additional external funding, new partnerships, new publications, etc.). Items on this evaluation survey also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the MSC approach.

Figure 1. Evaluation Data Sources

Data Analysis. The T&E team analyzes data and shares the findings with the RP2 leadership via dashboard and evaluation reports.

Individual Dashboards

The T&E team summarizes the data findings from the bimonthly evaluation surveys (per awardee) into individualized data summaries/dashboards and shares them with the RP2 team before the subsequent data collection time point. The T&E team codes open-ended response items as categorical variables. Qualitative data include questions about project challenges, roadblocks, and improvements to RADx-UP CDCC support or resources.

Quarterly Aggregate Dashboards

The T&E team aggregates bimonthly evaluation survey data across projects (included data are from projects' most recent completed survey) into quarterly dashboards that contain information about:

- Communities served
- Partner organization types
- Project enrollment and testing numbers
- Challenges reported
- Research products developed
- CDCC Impact and satisfaction

See [Appendix 2](#) for the most recently developed RADx-UP RP2 Quarterly Dashboard Report.

Biannual T&E Evaluation Reports

The T&E team analyzes data from all bimonthly evaluation surveys across projects and presents the findings in biannual evaluation reports (e.g. 6-month and 12-month program reports).

Project Impact Profiles. The T&E team utilizes 6-month and closeout survey data to create Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) Project impact profiles⁶. The RP2 and the T&E teams will co-develop each project’s profile with the respective project. The profiles provide a high-level description of how project outcomes reported on the 12-month closeout survey align with impact areas of the model, as shown in the **Figure 2** below.

The TSBM is a framework designed to support the assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts² (see **Figure 2**). The T&E team will use the core components of the TSBM to evaluate the impact of the RP2 program in demonstrating the clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities. The main contribution of the TSBM is its utility in identifying the core areas where testing outreach and strategies developed through the RADx-UP program provide clinical, public health, economic, and policy benefits. The T&E team will also include an additional impact indicator – health equity, to describe the impact profiles of projects that focus on dismantling inequities and addressing the Social Determinants of Health in testing among underserved populations.

Figure 2. Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)^{2, 6} + Health Equity Impact Areas

<p>CLINICAL</p>	<p>Clinical and Medical Benefits (procedures, guidelines, tools, and products)</p>
<p>COMMUNITY</p>	<p>Community and Public Health Benefits (health activities, care, and promotion)</p>
<p>ECONOMIC</p>	<p>Economic Benefits (commercial products, financial savings, and benefits)</p>
<p>HEALTH EQUITY</p>	<p>Health Equity Benefits* (accessibility, adaptability, reach)</p>

	<p>Policy and Legislative Benefits (advisory activities, policies, and legislation)</p>
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*The TSBM Framework has been adapted for this evaluation to include an indicator for Health Equity benefits.

Most Significant Change. The Most Significant Change (MSC) technique is an evaluation method that involves collecting significant change stories from the field, and having a panel of designated stakeholders select the most significant of these stories³. This informs program impact and unintended changes, how and when a change came to be, and also helps provide an understanding on the values of different stakeholders. The MSC approach will be incorporated into the 18-month follow up survey. The survey will include an open text question asking respondents to share what they felt was the most significant change that resulted from their project.

III. Results

This evaluation reports details the results from the bimonthly evaluation surveys collected between January 1 through December 31, 2022, and analyzed and summarized across projects.

A. Process Evaluation Results

RP2 Program Grant Application Process and Award Utilization

Currently, there are **19 RP2 projects across funding cycles** (Cycle 1 n=8 funded projects; Cycle 2 n=1 funded project; there were no funded projects in Cycle 3, Cycle 4 n=4 funded projects, Cycle 5 n=3 projects, Cycle 6 n=3 projects). **Table 2** below shows the metrics per RP2 funding cycle for the application process and notification of awards.

The average number of days between award notification and project initiation varied by cycle. For cycles 1 and 2, we used the Notice of Award (NoA) date for award notification. For cycle 4 and all cycles moving forward, we will use the activation date rather than the NoA date, as NIH no longer requires the NoA date for projects deemed less than minimal risk by their IRB of record. Removing the NoA requirement reduced the average number of days between award notification and project initiation.

Table 2. Metrics per RP2 Funding Cycle for the Grant Application Process, Notification of Award, and Funding Expenditure by Awardees

RP2 Project Cycle	Application Period	Number of Applicants per cycle	Number of Projects Awarded per cycle	Successful Application Rate	Average number of days between award notification and Project initiation
Cycle 1	3/3/21 – 5/28/21	9	8	88.8%	182
Cycle 2	5/7/21 - 8/2/21	5	1	20%	79
Cycle 3	6/19/21 - 8/13/21	0	0	-	-
Cycle 4	10/29/21 - 2/1/22	8	4	50%	90 [^]
Cycle 5	4/1/22 – 7/8/22	3	3	100%	72
Cycle 6*	8/5/22 - 11/14/22	7	3	43%	NA
Cycle 7*	11/15/22 – 1/13/23	11	6	55%	NA

*Cycle 6 and 7 projects have not yet begun and are not included in this report.

[^]One of the four projects had a significantly long period compared to the other three projects, which changed the average from 66 to 90 days.

In this report, we present data from 2-month, 4-month, 6-month, 8-month, 10-month, and 12-month timepoints for:

- Cycle 1 n=8 of 8 total projects
- Cycle 2 n =1 of 1 total project
- Cycle 4 n= 4 of 4 total projects
- Cycle 5 n= 3 of 3 total projects

Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support. Figure 3 summarizes the results from the 6-month evaluation survey regarding project satisfaction with the application and award process. Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support regarding the application process. **Over 83% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with each statement** that asked about receiving adequate support to completing their application and having an RFA that was easy to understand to projects.

Figure 3. RP2 Project Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support (n= 12 projects reporting)

Satisfaction with the support provided by the RP2 administration team. Figure 4 summarizes the results from the 6-month evaluation survey regarding project satisfaction with the support provided by the RP2 administration team. Overall, projects reported satisfaction with the RP2 administration team. **Over 83% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with each statement.**

Figure 4. RP2 Project Satisfaction support provided by the RP2 administration team (n= 12 projects reporting)

B. Outcome Evaluation Results

B1. Participant Completion Rates

Survey Completion. The T&E team has seen close to a 100% survey completion rate across cycles. This is in part due to the processes that the T&E team and the RP2 Leadership team have put in place to ensure survey completion in a timely manner. The T&E team uses REDCap, a secure web application, to manage the evaluation surveys. For projects that do not respond to the automated email containing the survey invitation link, the T&E team communicates with the RP2 Leadership team to have them send out an email reminder. Over the past year, there have been a number of surveys that have not been responded to just by sending out automated survey invitations via REDCap, but this additional touchpoint with projects tends to promote survey completion.

Figure 6. RP2 Project Institution Type (*n*= 13* projects reporting)
 *Only five projects of the 13 reported fell within the categories included in the figure.

Underserved Populations Served. See [Figure 7](#) for a breakdown of underserved populations served by RP2 projects. Underserved populations are *populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors*¹². **This data shows that RP2 projects have a broad reach of underserved populations-** all populations that fall within underserved populations are being reached. Of the projects reported during this reporting period, **the most common underserved population served by RP2 projects continue to be socioeconomically disadvantaged populations.**

Figure 7. Underserved Populations Served by Projects (*n*= 16 projects reporting)

COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served. See [Figure 8](#) for a breakdown of COVID-19 vulnerable communities served by RP2 projects. COVID-19 vulnerable communities are *populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19*¹³. When taken together, **RP2 projects have a wide reach of COVID-19 vulnerable communities**; all communities that fall within the COVID-19 vulnerable communities are being reached. Of the projects reported during this period, **residents of nursing homes and assisted living facilities continue to be the most common COVID-19 vulnerable communities served by RP2 projects across cycles.**

Figure 8. COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served by Projects (*n= 16 projects reporting*)

Characteristics of RP2 Projects’ Partners. [Figure 9](#) refers to the project's community partner organizations. Twelve projects reported having any type of partner. **Most project partners are classified as community organizations or faith-based organizations**, but in Cycle 4 we are starting to see more local government partners which could include public health departments or social service agencies.

Figure 9. Characteristics of RP2 Projects’ Partners (*n= 12 projects reporting*)

B3. RP2 Project Testing and Enrollment Outcomes

RP2 Projects Testing and Enrollment. One of the main aims of the RP2 program is to improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations. **Figure 10** shows the target participant enrollment number as well as the number of participants enrolled across cycles one, two, four, and five. This data informs the program outcome of increasing numbers of individuals reached with testing services or information. Of the 10 projects reported, **there have been a total of 1,778 participants of the 4,120 participants (43.2%) they are targeting to enroll by the end of their project period.**

Figure 10. Number of Participants Enrolled: Actual vs Target (*n= 10 projects reporting*)

Figure 11 shows the number of tests administered versus planned to administer versus actually administered to participants across eleven projects, with **a total of 2,099 tests administered out of the 8,600 total tests (24.4%) they are targeting to administer by the end of their project period across all cycles.**

Figure 11. Number of Tests Administered: Actual vs Target (*n= 9 projects reporting*)

Challenges Experienced by Projects. The T&E team also asked projects to report on any roadblocks or challenges faced so far in completing their project. The bimonthly evaluation surveys include noting challenges relating to sample collection, challenges to testing, test result reporting, and engaging with community members. The T&E team reviewed these challenges and coded the responses into several categories.

Of the 12 projects that reported on challenges experienced, **the most common were related to enrollment and testing reporting challenges.** *Enrollment challenge* are defined as challenges/delays in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site has been established. *Testing reporting challenges* are defined as challenges in obtaining results from tests or reporting test results to patients. **Table 3** lists the codes that the T&E team developed for responses to questions that ask projects *to describe any challenges to sample collection, testing, test result reporting, engaging with community members, and any other challenges not mentioned.* *Pandemic-related delays* were more common during earlier cycles possibly due to COVID surges during the earlier part of the year. Another common challenge mentioned by projects is the delay in beginning recruitment and testing due to waiting on IRB approval.

As challenges are observed, the T&E team is communicating these challenges to leadership so they can be addressed promptly. Testing reporting, partnerships, and enrollment challenges may be opportunities for the RP2 team to strategize how to address those challenges with projects.

Table 3. Challenges Experienced by Projects

Code	Quotes
Administrative	<i>"Hiring and contracts take a great deal of time before we can create workflows for our RP2."</i>
Pandemic-Related Delays	<i>"COVID-related lockdowns in study setting delayed data collection."</i>
Enrollment	<i>"Our major challenge was that home test kits were readily available by the time we rolled our study out, thus the demand for PCR testing was less in the community."</i>
Testing Administration	<i>"Saliva collection is not an optional method for minors ages 3-12 years old. Salivating in a test tube is difficult for them or they may not understand the instructions."</i>
Regulatory	<i>"To update the testing method, I submitted a modification form to the IRB in early February, but there is a delay to get it approved."</i>
Partnerships	<i>"We are collaborating with the [name of city] Parks and Recreation Department. We have run into challenges scheduling with them in the early summer due to the start of summer programs. Now that those are now underway, we anticipate closer collaboration with them now."</i>

Testing Procurement	<i>"The Flu/Covid-19 combo tests are on back order with an estimated delivery date of 8/26. Most of the interested participants want to have the combo tests and we couldn't offer them for now..."</i>
Testing Reporting	<i>"Some community members don't have email address, which is the major reporting method used by [the] testing center. We just have to call their cell phone to inform the testing results."</i>

B3. RP2 Project Outcomes and Impacts

RP2 Project Outcomes Aligned with the Translational Sciences Benefit Model (TSBM) Indicators. In this section, we summarize the results from the 6-month evaluation survey regarding the RP2 project's impacts and plans for sustainability of their research and project activities. Projects are asked to list their main project outcomes and for each outcome listed, they are asked to indicate the impact area of the Translational Sciences Benefit Model with which it best aligns. This information is used to evaluate the impact of the RP2 program in demonstrating the clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities. Currently when asked to report on project outcomes and with what TSBM key benefit area these outcomes fall within, **the majority of project outcomes reported on fall within the Community and Public Health impact area, followed by the Clinical impact area** (see [figure 12](#)). Many project outcomes reported are related to promoting and increasing COVID-19 testing uptake and accessibility among different target communities. This was done, for example, through assessments to understand the barriers and facilitators to COVID-19 testing uptake, implementation of culturally-tailored telehealth education sessions delivered by community health workers, and identifying benefits and challenges of shelter-based rapid testing on shelter operations. Some clinical outcomes reported include frequency of community identification as a hot spot or testing desert pre and post-intervention, and provide a new tool to diagnose SARS-Cov2 in clinical settings.

Currently, only three projects have received their 12-month closeout survey. Still, once these data are collected, the T&E Team will develop Impact Profiles for each project to reflect how project outcomes reported on the 12-month closeout survey align with impact areas of the TSBM framework. See [Appendix 3](#) for an example of one of the individual Impact Profiles.

Figure 12. RP2 Project Outcomes Aligned with the TSBM Indicators (*n= 10 projects reporting*)

Projects’ Research Products. The T&E team tracks peer-reviewed publications along with other RADx-UP publications in our T&E Publications Tracking. In addition to scholarly publications, the T&E team seeks to understand additional products that projects are developing and disseminating. **Figure 13** breaks down the types of research products that projects have developed. **Over half of the projects reporting have developed more than one research product.**

Figure 13. RP2 Research Products (*n= 11 projects reporting*)

IV. Recommendations and Conclusion

Recommendations. This section details process and outcome-related recommendations for improving the RP2 program based on conclusions from the bimonthly evaluation surveys. These recommendations aim to support continuous program improvement, delivery, and quality of administrative support.

1. **Continue to fund a diverse range of projects to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.**
 - Continue to fund projects representing geographically diverse, underserved, and Covid-19 vulnerable communities. Some areas/populations to focus on recruiting in the future include:
 - West, Northwest, and Eastern regions of the US
 - Recruiting projects that represent tribal nations
 - States where there is an increased COVID-19 incidence and/or mortality rate
2. **Address challenges cited by projects**
 - Projects report challenges related to participant enrollment, administrative tasks such as funding and staffing, testing reporting, and testing administration.
 - Of the 12 projects that reported on challenges experienced, **the most common were related to enrollment and testing reporting challenges.**
 - *Enrollment challenge* are defined as challenges/delays in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site has been established.
 - *Testing reporting challenges* are defined as challenges in obtaining results from tests or reporting test results to patients.
 - Maintaining continuous feedback loops between the UNC T&E team, the RP2 Leadership team, and RP2 awardees

Conclusion. The T&E team aims to measure and assess the RP2 program’s productivity and progress toward program aims and outcomes. The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the RP2 program’s effectiveness, performance, and community engagement. The T&E team achieves it through bimonthly evaluation surveys distributed to funded projects and tracking of program records. The purpose of this interim evaluation report is to cover the evaluation of the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) projects from January 1 through December 31, 2022. Currently, there are 19 RP2 Projects across funding cycles (Cycle 1 n=8 funded projects; Cycle 2=1 funded project; there were no funded projects in Cycle 3, Cycle 4=4 funded projects, Cycle 5=3 funded projects, Cycle 6 n=3 funded projects). A total of 1,778 participants have been enrolled, and 2,099 tests have been administered across cycles.

Next Steps. In the remainder of the RP2 program, the T&E team will continue to:

1. Monitor program progress through bimonthly evaluation surveys and reports will be completed every six months.

2. Create: (i) **Individual Project Impact Profiles** to be shared with each project to highlight project outcomes and benefits and (ii) an **Aggregate RP2 Impact Profile** to visualize program-level outcomes and TSBM benefits across projects.
3. Additionally, the T&E will distribute an 18-month (six months post-project) survey to assess the longer-term impacts of the pilot projects, including any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.).
4. The T&E team is also in the process of developing an **Impact Assessment tool** to **further measure the health equity impacts across projects**. The next reporting period will include finalizing the tool with the input of RP2 administrative leadership team and RP2 projects and implementing the tool as a part of data collection.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model

Rapid Research Pilots Evaluation Logic Model

Appendix 2. RADx-UP RP2 Quarterly Dashboard Report

Data collected from Jan. 1, 2022 to Dec. 31, 2022. See Appendix for list of projects and timepoints included in the report.

15

Projects Reporting

19

Projects Awarded

Projects by Cycle

Latest Survey Completed by Projects

Inactive Projects

Projects from Minority-Serving Institutions

Communities Served

49

Underserved Communities

49

COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Underserved Communities

COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Partner Organization Types

46

Partner Organizations

Partner Organizations by Type

Cumulative Enrollment

1,778

Participants Enrolled to Date

21%

Enrollment Target Reached

Cumulative Testing

9

Projects Reporting

Tests Kits Used by Projects

2,099

Tests Administered

15%

Testing Target Reached

122 (5.8%)

Positive Tests

Challenges

21

Challenges Reported

Type of Challenges Reported by Projects

Research Products

18

Research Products

Type of Research Products Reported by Projects

CDCC Overall

Ease of accessing support

Effectively addressing feedback received from projects

Effectiveness

Overall helpfulness

Promptness of support delivery

CDCC Services

11

Projects Reporting

CDCC Support Services Used

Most Frequently Used CDCC Support Services

Level of Satisfaction with RP2 Admin and Leadership

Level of Satisfaction with Comms

Level of Satisfaction with Testing Support

Level of Satisfaction with Testing Procurement

Level of Satisfaction with WGs

Level of Satisfaction with CCPH

CDCC Impact

The CDCC support services increased my project's understanding of community engagement approaches

The CDCC support services increased my project's application of community-engagement approaches in connecting with my project's communities

The knowledge gained from the CCPH office hours was useful for my project

Appendix

Tests Kits Used by Projects

Project	Test Kit	Test Type
R0101	TaqPath COVID-19 Combo Kit	PCR
R0102	iHealth COVID-19 Antigen Rapid Test	Rapid Antigen
R0103	Hologic Panther Fusion® SARS-CoV-2 assay	PCR
R0103	LDT Lamp	PCR
R0103	Panther Fusion® SARS-CoV-2 Assay	PCR
R0103	Sofia Quidel Antigen test	Rapid Antigen
R0103	Sofia SARS Antigen Fluorescent Immunoassay (FIA)	Rapid Antigen
R0104	Abbott BinaxNOW COVID-19 Ag Card	Rapid Antigen
R0105	Abbott BinaxNOW Self-Test	Rapid Antigen
R0105	FlowFlex COVID-19 Antigen Home Test	Rapid Antigen
R0106	Roche 6800, Panther Aptima and the DiaSorin Integrated Cyclor	PCR
R0107	QuickVue At-Home OTC COVID-19 2 Test Kits	Rapid Antigen
R0109	TaqPath COVID-19 Fast PCR Combo Kit 2.0	PCR
R0109	Yale SalivaDirect™ COVID-19 Test	PCR
R0204	Quantstudio 5 or 7 real-time PCR; CDC 2019-nCoV Real-Time RT-PCR Diagnostic Panel	PCR
R0401	FlowFlex COVID-19 Antigen Home Test	Rapid Antigen
R0401	iHealth COVID-19 Antigen Rapid Test	Rapid Antigen
R0401	Sofia 2 Flu + SARS Antigen FIA (flu A/B)	Rapid Antigen
R0405	LumiraDx Antigen Test	Rapid Antigen
R0405	LumiraDx SARS-CoV-2 Ab Test	Antibody
R0405	TaqPath™ COVID-19 Fast PCR Combo Kit 2.0	PCR
R0406	cobas Liat SARS-CoV-2 & Influenza AB	PCR
R0503	iHealth COVID-19 Antigen Rapid Test	Rapid Antigen

Projects Reporting

Project	Cycle	Last Timepoint Completed
R0101	1	10
R0102	1	12
R0103	1	10
R0104	1	12
R0105	1	10
R0106	1	12
R0107	1	8
R0109	1	12
R0204	2	12
R0401	4	6
R0405	4	8
R0406	4	6
R0408	4	2
R0501	5	2
R0503	5	2

Glossary

Minority-Serving Institution: Institutions focused on serving minority students. More information about institution types can be found [here](#).

Abbreviation	Minority-Serving Institution
AANAPI-Serving	Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution
HBCU	Historically Black College and University
Hispanic-Serving	Hispanic-Serving Institution
Non-MSI	Non-Minority-Serving Institution
TCU	Tribal College or University

Underserved Community: Populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors. More information can be found [here](#) and [here](#).

Abbreviation	Underserved Community
AIAN	American Indians/Alaska Natives
Asian	Asian Americans
Black	Blacks/African Americans
Latino	Hispanics/Latinos
LowSES	Socioeconomically disadvantaged populations
NHPI	Native Hawaiians and other Pacific Islanders
Rural	Rural and remote communities; underserved rural populations
SGM	Sexual and gender minorities

COVID-19 Vulnerable Community: Populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19. More information can be found [here](#).

Abbreviation	COVID-19 Vulnerable Community
Child	Children and adolescents
Cognition	Individuals with cognitive impairment or dementia, or communication disorders
Comorbidities	Individuals with medical comorbidities known to increase risk of severe COVID-19
Congregate Housing	Individuals living in congregate housing such as shelters or residential treatment facilities
Elderly	Community-dwelling older adults
EnvRisk	Communities exposed to high rates of air pollution or other toxic exposures
Homeless	Homeless populations
Immigrants	Migrant and immigrant communities
MentalHealth	Individuals with substance use disorders or serious mental illness
Pregnant	Pregnant and post-partum women
Public Housing	Individuals in overcrowded or public housing
Rural	Rural and remote communities; underserved rural populations
TribalNation	Residents of tribal lands or reservations

Abbreviation	CDCC Service
CCPH	Community Campus Partnerships for Health office hours and community engagement consultations
Comms	Communication support services (e.g. RADx-UP website, myRADxUP home portal, newsletter, project-wide meetings, etc.)
Data Informaticist Support	Data Informaticist support
Data Intake Reviews	Data intake reviews (For CDE uploads)
ERC	Engagement Resource Center
Other	Other
RADX-UP CDCC Data Upload	RADX-UP CDCC Data Upload
RP2 Admin and Leadership	Rapid Research Pilot Program administration and leadership
Statistical Support and Consultations	Statistical support and consultations
Testing Procurement	Testing procurements and vendor management
Testing Support	Testing support and guidance services
WGs	Working Groups

Appendix 3. RADx-UP RP2 Impact Profile

Community Health Worker Led COVID-19 Education and Rapid Antigen Testing for People Experiencing Homelessness

This study aims to evaluate the feasibility of COVID-19 rapid antigen testing in a homeless shelter setting and community health worker (CHW) education to inform future infection control, diagnostic and screening technology implementation efforts, and pandemic response for people experiencing homelessness (PEH).

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The project resulted in community and public health benefits. By engaging the target population through CHW-delivered educational focus groups, the project leveraged CHW's rapport with the community and contributed to knowledge gains and helped change perspectives around testing and vaccines. Interviews with PEH and staff revealed benefits and challenges to rapid testing in a shelter, including motivators and barriers to testing among PEH. Lessons learned from this can be used to inform future pandemic planning for homeless shelters, and demonstrates the importance of infrastructure to support diagnostic technology in pandemic response.

The Challenge

Rapid identification of COVID cases is critical to preventing further transmission, yet despite CDC recommendations for regular COVID-19 testing in congregate settings, homeless shelters have faced substantial barriers to testing including limited capacity, lack of transportation, and issues with client acceptability and mistrust. These barriers, along with common delays in receiving lab-based test results, increased demand for shelter beds, and an overall lack of prevention guidance support, have caused service disruptions and shelter shutdowns for extremely vulnerable homeless populations.

The Approach

The specific aims of this study are to:

- Examine the effect of CHW-led education on the COVID-related knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs of PEH
- Identify barriers and motivators to shelter-based COVID rapid testing among PEH
- Understand the role and impact of rapid testing on shelter operations and guest daily activities

Contact: Dr. Natalia Rodriguez, Project Principal Investigator and Assistant Professor, Purdue University, natalia@purdue.edu

Find out more: healthtechquitylab.org

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The project resulted in...

76 CHW-led educational focus group participants

55 rapid assessment surveys and **41** qualitative interviews with PEH who were tested at the shelter

14 qualitative interviews with staff

Round Table Presentation at APHA 2022 Conference, Title: *Community Health Worker Led COVID-19 Education and Rapid Testing for People Experiencing Homelessness*

Publication: Rodriguez, N.M., Martinez, R.G., Ziolkowski, R. et al. "COVID knocked me straight into the dirt": perspectives from people experiencing homelessness on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMC Public Health* 22, 1327 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13748-y>

Key Benefits

COMMUNITY

COVID related knowledge gains and improved attitudes toward testing and vaccination among people experiencing homelessness.

COMMUNITY

Motivators and barriers to shelter-based COVID rapid testing among PEH to inform and tailor educational resources for PEH for COVID testing

COMMUNITY

Benefits and challenges to rapid testing in a homeless shelter to inform future emergency planning in this setting.

Translational Science Benefits Model¹

